

Comprehensive Review of the Genetic Polymorphism of *Schistosoma mansoni* and Drug Resistance: Human vs. Intermediate Host Perspective

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- 1.Safwa GeneralGeneral
- 2.Qatif central hospital
- 3.Dhahran eye specialist hospital
- 4.Comprehensive Screening Center
- 5.King fahad phc
- 6.Maternity and children hospital
- 7.Al Oyoum City Hospital
- 8.Dammam health network
9. AlFaisal PHC
- 10.Primary Health Care Center Shoba Almubarraz
- 11.King fahad hospital hofuf
- 12.Primary health care

ABSTRACT

Schistosoma mansoni, the causative agent of intestinal schistosomiasis, exhibits substantial genetic polymorphism, contributing to its adaptability and resistance to praziquantel (PZQ), the mainstay treatment for schistosomiasis. This review explores the genetic mechanisms underlying *S. mansoni* diversity, emphasizing its role in drug resistance and interactions with human (definitive) and snail (intermediate) hosts. Genetic variation in *S. mansoni* is driven by sexual reproduction, recombination, and host-parasite co-evolution, with key contributions from microsatellites, mitochondrial DNA, and single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). While human immune responses and PZQ administration impose selective pressures, snail hosts shape genetic compatibility and transmission dynamics. Evidence suggests that high genetic diversity enhances immune evasion and influences drug susceptibility, complicating control efforts. Comparative analysis of human and snail host influences reveals distinct yet interconnected drivers of parasite evolution. Integrative strategies combining genomic surveillance, snail control, and novel therapeutics are essential for managing drug resistance and sustaining schistosomiasis control efforts.

1. Introduction

Schistosoma mansoni, a parasitic trematode causing intestinal schistosomiasis, affects millions worldwide, primarily in sub-Saharan Africa and South America(1). Its lifecycle alternates between humans (definitive host) and freshwater snails (*Biomphalaria* spp.) as intermediate hosts. The parasite's genetic diversity plays a pivotal role in its adaptability to environmental pressures and resistance to praziquantel (PZQ), the frontline treatment for schistosomiasis(2). A deeper understanding of the genetic mechanisms influencing host-parasite interactions and drug resistance is essential for effective disease control.

2. Genetic Polymorphism in *Schistosoma mansoni*

Genetic polymorphism underpins the adaptability of *S. mansoni* to its hosts and environmental challenges. This diversity results from sexual reproduction, recombination, and host-parasite co-evolution. Genetic diversity in *Schistosoma mansoni* populations: implications for control.(3).

2.1 Mechanisms of Genetic Variation

- **Microsatellite Markers:** Microsatellites are widely used to assess genetic diversity and structure in *S. mansoni* populations(4).

- **Mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA):** mtDNA analysis has revealed gene flow and evolutionary relationships among geographically distinct populations(5).
- **Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs):** SNP studies have linked genetic variation to traits such as drug resistance and host specificity(6).

2.2 Implications of Polymorphism

High genetic diversity within *S. mansoni* populations facilitates:

- Enhanced adaptability to human immune responses (7)
- Variability in drug susceptibility, affecting treatment outcomes.

3. Drug Resistance in *Schistosoma mansoni*

Resistance to praziquantel has been documented in several regions, raising concerns about its long-term efficacy. Schistosomiasis control: Present and future.(9)

3.1 Mechanisms of Resistance

- **Selection Pressure:** Frequent use of PZQ in mass drug administration (MDA) campaigns promotes the selection of resistant genotypes.
- **Mutations in Drug Target Genes:** Resistance is associated with mutations in calcium channel genes targeted by PZQ.
- **Genetic Bottlenecks:** Reduced genetic diversity in isolated populations due to MDA campaigns may amplify resistance traits(10).

3.2 Evidence from Studies

- Studies in Senegal and Egypt identified *S. mansoni* strains with reduced susceptibility to PZQ, emphasizing the importance of monitoring resistance markers
- SNP analyses have identified candidate resistance genes in experimental and field populations.

4. Host-Specific Dynamics

The lifecycle of *S. mansoni* involves dual host systems, with selective pressures imposed by both human and snail hosts shaping genetic diversity.

4.1 Human Hosts

Humans exert selective pressures through:

- **Immune Responses:** Genetic diversity in *S. mansoni* enables immune evasion, promoting the survival of specific genotypes(11).
- **Drug Pressure:** PZQ treatment applies strong selective pressure, driving the evolution of resistant strains

4.2 Intermediate Hosts (Snails)

Snail hosts influence *S. mansoni* polymorphism through:

- **Genetic Compatibility:** Snail genetic diversity determines compatibility with *S. mansoni* strains, affecting transmission dynamics.
- **Population Bottlenecks:** Low genetic diversity in snail populations may constrain *S. mansoni* genetic variability.

5. Comparative Analysis: Human vs. Intermediate Hosts

Table 1: Human vs. Intermediate Hosts

Aspect	Human Host	Intermediate Host (Snails)
Selective Pressure	Immune system and drug treatments	Genetic compatibility and environment
Genetic Diversity	Higher, driven by immune evasion	Lower, constrained by snail genetics
Drug Resistance	More pronounced due to MDA	Indirect via parasite adaptation
Polymorphism Impact	Affects virulence and drug efficacy	Influences transmission dynamics

6. Implications for Control Strategies

❖ Integrated Approaches:

- Combine MDA with snail control to limit transmission and mitigate drug resistance risks.

❖ Genomic Surveillance:

- Implement whole-genome sequencing to track resistance markers and monitor population dynamics.

❖ Novel Drug Development:

- Design multi-target drugs to address the genetic variability of *S. mansoni*

Conclusion

The genetic polymorphism of *Schistosoma mansoni* significantly impacts its adaptability, virulence, and resistance to praziquantel. The selective pressures exerted by human and snail hosts shape this diversity, influencing treatment efficacy and transmission. Continued research into host-parasite interactions and genomic surveillance is essential for sustainable schistosomiasis control.

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